

Two methods of land leveling

D. Luzes and P. Lynce, Agronomy Department, Lisbon Agricultural University, Tapada Da Ajuda, Lisbon, Portugal

Land leveling is an important operation in irrigated rice.

We tested two methods of land leveling during 1988 and 1989 dry seasons on 2 ha in the Sado Valley. Soil was a hydromorphic, sandy loam with pH 5.6 and 0.8% organic C.

In the conventional, rather drastic method of leveling, *Rebaixa*, the field is flooded and a tractor mounted with an iron blade is used for leveling. The water level serves to orient the operator's work. Rice seed is soaked 24 h before planting into the flooded field.

We tested using laser equipment with a land plane to level and seed the dry field (as is done in the United States and Australia). Fields are flooded 24 h after seeding.

Effects on the crop are shown in the table. Seeds/m² cannot be counted

Effect of 2 ways to level ricefields. Portugal, Sado, 1988-89. Ringo variety seeded 6 May 1988 and 5 May 1989 dry seasons.

Method	Seed (kg/ha)	Seeds (no./m ²)	Plants (no./m ²)	Survival (%)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)
1988						
Conventional	161	568	116	21	171	4.6
Laser	200	628	205	33	243	7.1
LSD (0.05)	-	-	31		ns	1.4
1989						
Conventional	180	565	192	34	319	7.7
Laser	217	641	353	55	438	10.2
LSD (0.05)	-	-	65		ns	1.5

because of water turbidity after flooding. We based that calculation on kg/ha and 1,000-grain weight (31.8 g). Tests indicated 97% germination at 20 and 25 °C. Plants were counted at different growth stages.

The major difference between the two techniques was plant survival. The most critical phase is between seeding and emergence; germination has a strong influence on development of the productive population.

The main factors responsible for reduction in population are low oxygen diffusion due to the high water level (20 cm) and low light transmittal. We assume that the decrease in available light intensity with the conventional method is the main reason for the comparatively low survival.

The difference between 1988 and 1989 was due mainly to a higher average temperature and radiation flux in 1989. □

Effect of coated urea on yield, N uptake, recovery, and response of rice and succeeding wheat crop

G. Singh and O. P. Singh, N.D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Crop Research Station, Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, UP, India

We studied the effect of modified urea on yield and N uptake of wet season rice and the residual effect on a succeeding dry season wheat crop in 1988-89. Soil was clay loam with pH 8.2 and 0.42% organic C. Four forms of urea, two N levels, and three application schedules (12 treatments) were laid out in a random block design with four replications.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of rice variety Mahsuri were transplanted 22 Jul 1988 at 15- x 15-cm spacing. Wheat variety HD 1553 was sown 25 Dec 1988 with an additional 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha.

Effect of coated urea on rice yield, N uptake, N recovery, and on following wheat yield. CRS, Ghagharaghat, UP, India, 1988-89.

Treatment ^a	Rice yield (t/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)	Fertilizer N recovery (%)	Wheat yield (t/ha)
Control	2.5	23.9	-	0.7
30 PU (3 S)	3.2	30.3	21.3	1.0
60 PU (3 S)	3.4	33.3	15.6	1.1
30 MRPU (B)	3.3	32.8	29.6	1.5
60 MRPU (B)	3.7	41.1	28.6	1.7
60 MRPU (2 S)	4.0	44.4	34.5	1.8
30 NCU (B)	3.7	41.1	57.3	1.7
60 NCU (B)	4.2	50.3	44.0	2.0
60 NCU (2 S)	4.4	53.8	49.8	2.1
30 GCU (B)	3.5	34.4	35.0	1.6
60 GCU (B)	3.9	39.7	26.3	1.7
60 GCU (2 S)	4.2	43.7	36.3	1.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3	6.0	4.1	0.2

^a PU = prilled urea, MRPU = Musooriephos-coated urea, NCU = neem cake-coated urea, GCU = gypsum-coated urea, B = basal, S = split, 3S = (50% basal + 25% at tillering + 25% at panicle initiation stage), 2S = (1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressed at tillering).

Treatments showed significant differences in rice and wheat yields (see table). Yields were significantly greater with neem-coated (NCU) than with Musooriephos-coated urea

(MPCU). Yields with NCU and gypsum-coated urea (GCU) were comparable. The highest N uptake and N recovery were with NCU. □